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DESIGN VERIFICATION OF THE VEHICLE DEVELOPED FOR THE AMERICAN MARKET ACCORDING TO FMVSS-305 REGULATION WITH VIRTUAL ANALYSIS

Ayberk Gökçe, Ümit Dardeh

Karsan Automotive, R&D Department, Bursa, Turkey
Corresponding Author: Ayberk Gökçe, ayberk.gokce@karsan.com.tr

ABSTRACT

A rolling chassis that has been developed for the North America market was investigated in order to meet the requirements of FMVSS-305 with a frontal impact of 35 mph (56 km/h) velocity to the rigid wall and by using the results, design developments were conducted together with the developed finite element model. Design iterations were carried out together with the created virtual analysis model. Acceleration effect on the battery compartment during the crash and vehicle's structural and mechanical integrity was determined by using LS-DYNA explicit solver. Iterative design development studies were carried out to observe the non-continuous crash energy flow on the main carrier chassis rails (longitudinal member) during the crash with the front rigid wall. Also they were made to make the energy flow continuous and determine the insufficient structural strength of the vehicle during the intrusion with the side rigid pole and the entrances to the battery area and structural development studies.

Keywords: FMVSS-305, vehicle safety, crashworthiness, electrolyte spillage

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution, which is negatively affected by the emission nowadays, and the increasing need for energy and have created a trend towards the preference of electric vehicles. Although electric vehicles have the potential to achieve high energy efficiency and zero emissions, and have significant problems to overcome, their development and improvement continues around the world, especially in terms of driver and battery safety. Since frontal impact is the most common crash scenario and the battery is often expensive and heavy, both passenger safety and battery protection should be considered in electric vehicles. Battery safety has three interrelated aspects: electrical integrity, thermal integrity, and mechanical integrity. Mechanical integrity is the least thought of as safety, but the most vital aspect for electric vehicles. (Wierzbicki, 2010)

In a vehicle development project, before vehicle production, virtual verification software and methods are among the indispensable tools used by research and development companies within the scope of mechanical integrity and strength. Thanks to the virtual verification activities performed on the virtual vehicle, both the product development cycle can be rotated faster and the physical prototype and test costs are reduced. Due to this

positive effect on the time and cost parameters, which are very important for the automotive industry, the weight of virtual studies in product development studies is increasing day by day.

In vehicle projects, crash safety and driver-passenger safety parameters may vary according to the countries / regions where the vehicle will be used. Each country has some evaluation criterias specific to the region. These conditions, generally known as "regulation", are expected to be met in the relevant vehicle.

In this study, a vehicle developed for the American market was designed to meet the conditions of "front crash test on a rigid wall" according to FMVSS-305 and "crash test with side poll" according to FMVSS-214. It is based on improving passenger safety parameters with virtual verification. The issue of crash safety for electric vehicles was mentioned and the scenarios specific to battery safety were examined within the scope of compliance with the FMVSS-305 regulation. In the section related to crash safety, the preparation of the crash model and the solution made in LS-Dyna explicit solver, the examination of the results are emphasized and the design improvement studies of the crash model with the acceleration-time data taken from the crash model are explained.

2. SCOPE OF IMPACT TESTS

FMVSS-305 regulation examines the safety of passengers in case of frontal impact, side impact and rear impact for electric vehicles, and the prevention of electrolyte spillage from the batteries entering the driver and passenger compartments during the crash, so that they do not harm the driver and passenger.

In this part of the study, within the scope of the efforts to improve the front and side crash performance of a rolling chassis, “frontal impact on rigid wall at 48 km / h speed” specified in FMVSS 305 regulation and “side impact on rigid pole” at 32 km / h speed were carried out. Within the scope of FMVSS-214 regulation, there is a condition of “side impact to deformable barrier” at 56 km / h for side impact. However, since the vehicle is a rolling chassis, the condition of locally hitting a rigid pole at 32 km / h will cause locally higher deformation on the vehicle and the amount of interference to the battery will be at higher levels, and this condition has been preferred.

The rolling chassis model, in which development studies are carried out, includes the profile construction space frame structure Body-In-White, battery, electric motor, electronic components and chassis components. Other components of the vehicle (trim parts, driver's cabin, cargo cabin, etc.) are modeled by defining the mass from the connection points. There are a total of 2,381,779 2D-shell elements in the model (Figure 1, Figure 3).

Figure 1. Components of Rolling Chassis

While evaluating the results of the structural analysis, it was based on the electrolyte spillage or deterioration of the batteries and electric motor functionality after the crash and the prevention of battery electrolyte spillage attempts to the driver and passenger area with the deformation that will occur in the battery cells after the crash. In addition, with the LS-Dyna software, in order to evaluate the crash situation, the acceleration in the driver's area in case of a frontal impact on the rigid wall at 48 km/h

(Figure 2) and the side hitting the rigid pole at 32 km / h were obtained. During the crash, the structural condition of the vehicle and the maximum level of energy absorption and minimum acceleration to the driver and / or passenger were designed, and the thickness and shape optimization study was carried out on energy absorbing controlled folding zones with an iterative approach.

Figure 2. Acceleration/Time Graph of Frontal Impact

Figure 3. Rolling Chassis Vehicle Systems

3. IMPACT SIMULATION ON THE ROLLING CHASSIS VEHICLE

In this section, the G force values that will be reflected on the vehicle, driver and / or passenger in the vehicle model developed within the scope of frontal crash and side crash tests are calculated. Later, these G force values were again used with LS-Dyna to obtain "pass / fail" results for FMVSS 305. The graph of the acceleration-time values obtained from the iterations created with the current vehicle model and the changes applied subsequently and the energy conversions during the intrusion are included.

The main purpose is to ensure that the 2 batteries in the vehicle do not interfere or are at minimum level and that the battery connections within the scope of SAE J2464 can meet the loads generated during the crash.

3.1 FMVSS-305 Frontal Impact Simulation

In this section, according to FMVSS-305, the current state of the vehicle and the acceleration-time graphs of the improvements made by iterations under the conditions of "frontal impact test on a rigid wall" at a speed of 48 km / h are included.

Figure 4. Scenario of Frontal Impact Test on a Rigid Wall

Figure 5. Energy Change Graph

With the current vehicle structure, the transformation of the total energy of the vehicle into internal energy in the event of a frontal crash at a speed of 48 km / h is shown in Graphic-5. This graphic indicates that approximately 90% of the kinetic energy of the vehicle is transformed into internal energy. Ideally, all of the kinetic energy of the vehicle is expected to be absorbed by the crash elements. (Witteman, 1999) The impact elements of the rolling chassis vehicle are respectively formed as crash bars, crash dampers(cross member), and longitudinal members.

The acceleration starts depending on the time when the vehicle first comes into contact with a rigid wall and the intrusion begins. SEA (Specific Energy Absorption) formula represents the specific energy that can be absorbed after beginning of intrusion.

$$SEA = \frac{E_{abs}}{\rho \int_0^{\delta} A(h) dh}$$

The deformation of the crash-absorbing system of the vehicle starts and is completed in the 1st zone indicated in

Figure 6. In the 2. zone, the deformation of the area just behind the crash-damping system begins and is completed. Subsequently, the deformation of the longitudinal members extending along the length of the vehicle begins. In the current design, since the electric motor of the vehicle is mounted on the left longitudinal carrier member, the desired level of deformation was not achieved on this member. While this crash pulse value is expected to be in the range of 40-45 G in passenger vehicles as a reference point, since the crash pulse value generated in the current vehicle reaches the range of 50-60 G, it was needed to be developed by an iterative study.

Figure 6. Acceleration/Time Graph of Base Model

Figure 7. Base model Non-deformable Region

3.1.1 Development of FMVSS-305 Frontal Impact Simulation

In this section, there are iteration studies carried out in order to reduce the G force values that occur in the front crash scenario of the vehicle.

Development studies on the crash management system will be examined in three main sections: crash bar, crash damper(cross member), and longitudinal carrier member.

Since it will first come into contact with the rigid wall during the frontal impact, the stiffness level of the crash bar was primarily intended to be reduced. The profile section thickness of the structure used in the current design was reduced to 2 mm, as it was seen that the 3 mm sectioned structure was almost not deformed. (Figure 8)

Figure 8. Frontal impact improvement suggestions

The structure of the shock absorber system located behind the crash bar is currently in V shape form. It was seen in the first analysis that this design form was not deformed sufficiently on the vehicle. (Figure 9).

The cross-section of the sidemembers determines the geometry of the back of the crash-box. This is to ensure a reliable framework with sidemember support for the crash-box. Small geometrical variations are most common in the structure's corners. (Back 2010) To prevent bending collapse and create a damper effect on the longitudinal member in case of an angular impact its stiffness has to be developed to achieve a high bending resistance. For the cross-section of the profile, the bending resistance W in the undeformed state was calculated by the following;

$$W = (H^4 - h^4)/6H \text{ [mm}^3\text{]}$$

The energy absorption E , profile thickness t and column width H in the formula are based on the Wierzbicki theory, and iteration studies were carried out in the light of the following relationship while designing.

$$E \sim t^{5/3} \cdot H^{1/3}$$

Preferred to switch to the form of the longitudinal members in order to ensure the continuity of the cross-section form of the longitudinal members and to capture

the deformation at the desired level, which was formed by combining two profiles of 60x60x2 mm section thickness one on another by method welding process. (Figure 8).

In order to deform the impact-absorbing parts uniformly, there should be indentations or protruding structures called crash beads on the part. Uniform profile collapse flow that most important point of crashworthiness can be obtained by experiencing the accordion effect of the shock absorber system thanks to these indentations or protruding structures. The number and geometry of indentations or protrusions can be determined depending on the structure and dimensions of the part. (Witteman 1999)

The recesses or protrusions that should be present on the mentioned impact absorbing system can only be obtained from the molded production process. There are many restrictive factors in the production conditions of the profile structured vehicle. In the absence of high vehicle production numbers in mass production conditions, the methodologies used in the production of parts are also limited.

Figure 9. Base model in Crash Moment

In this case, in order to ensure the continuity of the cross-sectional form of the longitudinal carrier member and to capture deformation, the structure to be obtained by joining two interlocking C-section sheets by welding process was preferred. Thickness optimization study of this structure has been carried out. (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Crash Management System Thickness Optimization

Before the improvement studies were carried out, the maximum acceleration value on the left longitudinal carrier member was 56 G, but after the improvement it decreased to 44 G. Again, before the improvement work was done, the maximum acceleration value on the right longitudinal carrier member was 43 G, while it was seen as 42 G after the improvement. In the last case, the desired result is seen as close to G force values on the right and left longitudinal carrier member.

Figure 15. Body Structural Deformation Optimization Steps

The illustration of the G force values varying depending on the time on the vehicle can be seen in Figure 15. The deformation of the crash bar starts at 8 ms, the deformation of the impact-absorbing structure at 12 ms and the deformation of the longitudinal members after 20 ms and the energy is absorbed by the vertical (Z-axis) movement also can be seen formally.

After all these improvements, no deformation occurs in the batteries and battery connections in the vehicle in the frontal crash scenario. (Figure 16)

Figure 16. Stresses in the battery after analysis

3.2 FMVSS-214 Side Impact Simulation

In this section, the tests that must be done according to the FMVSS-214, which is the condition for side impact, referred to in FMVSS-305, are mentioned.

Figure 17. Crash Scenario with Side Rigid Wall

FMVSS 305 regulation for the side impact condition includes the case of crash with the moving deformable barrier (MDB) at 54 km / h. However, since the vehicle under development is a movable chassis, the A pillar ends at the steering level and there is no B pillar. In this case, "side poll with a rigid pole" conditions were preferred at a speed of 32 km / h, as it would cause a higher level of damage locally and would be more challenging. Between the A and B pillars, there are acceleration-time graphs of the current state of the vehicle and the improvements made by iterations in the axis of the driver's head at an angle of 75 degrees. (Figure 17).

The most challenging crash condition will be the side crash scenario, due to the fact that the batteries are in the center front of the vehicle and its current geometric structure. The structural projection of the left side of the vehicle where the driver zone step is located is given in Figure 18. As can be seen in the projection before and after the crash started, the batteries have a displacement of approximately 135 mm. (Figure 19)

Figure 18. Before/After Side Poll Impact Situation

Figure 19. Subjected Deformation on Battery

In this case, the amount of deformation in the batteries also will be high. For this reason, development work should be done in the side impact scenario.

3.2.1 FMVSS-214 Side Impact Simulation Improvements and Results

In this section, the iteration studies carried out in order to reduce the high deformation force values that occur in the side crash scenario of the vehicle are included. It will be necessary to make iterations so that the left side area required for the protection of the battery located between the middle longitudinal carrier member can absorb the energy at the maximum level.

Bending stress occurs in the middle longitudinal carrier member with the effect of the interference force created by the energy present during the crash in the step region. Driver seat mounting bracket is also located on this middle longitudinal carrier member. Due to this tension, interference occurs between the middle longitudinal member and seat connection body structure and the batteries. (Figure 20)

Figure 20. Section view of current design post-collision

In order to prevent the rigid poll used during the intrusion from interfering to the longitudinal members, energy absorbing structures must be created. Additional structures have been added with the increase in thickness and cross-section of the existing body structural elements. (Figure 21)

Figure 21. Side impact improvement work-1

The displacement amount of 135 mm in the current vehicle was retreated to approximately 60 mm after the first few iterations. (Figure 22). However, since this amount of displacement is not sufficient, iteration studies should continue.

Figure 22. Deformation Ratio of Battery

In order to reduce the amount of displacement on the middle longitudinal carrier member, new development of structures have been defined between the lower and upper main rails. (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Side impact improvement work-2

By this way, two important structures are connected with each other and they work together during the intrusion. In particular, it is aimed to reduce the bending stress on the upper longitudinal carrier member. As a result of the latest improvement work, the amount of displacement has been reduced from about 60 mm to 10 mm. (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Final Design and Deformation Ratio

After all of these improvements, there is no interference in the lower battery of the two batteries in the vehicle in

the side crash - side poll scenario. In the upper battery, the amount of plastic deformation of 0.77 that occurred with the interference in the current situation was reduced to 0.27 as a result of iterations.

It is thought that FMVSS-214 test conditions can be met with the strain amount of 10 mm formed locally and at the top due to the geometric structure of the top battery. However, the present results were performed on the simulation-CAE without prototype crash test correlation. Therefore, the results show relative improvements in sidebar crash. However, according to FMVSS standards, a final decision such as test pass / fail cannot be made.

4. RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATION

As a result of the results in sections 3.1 and 3.2, the summary situation is as in Table 1. With the implementation of the improvement studies carried out, according to FMVSS-305 regulation, the absence of any intrusion in the batteries and the absence of any deterioration in the battery connections in the frontal crash scenario shows that the simulation results is positive. Within the scope of FMVSS-214 regulation, the amount of intrusion of 10 mm in the upper battery will be appropriate in the side impact scenario. However, the present results were performed on simulation (CAE) without prototype crash test correlation. Therefore, the results show relative improvements in sidebar crash. According to the FMVSS-214 reference in FMVSS-305, the side impact test is expected to be performed with a moving deformable barrier (MDB) at a speed of 54 km / h. For these reasons, the test is considered successful, but a final decision can be made in the real environment by applying MDB.

In order to be 100% sure of the accuracy of the analysis performed in frontal crash and side crash scenarios, crash tests can be performed in at least one vehicle in real environment, and their data can be taken and compared. In addition, since the vehicle is a movable chassis, it will be useful to see the results with a simple analysis over the final study where the iterations are applied after the driver's cabin and cargo area are also designed. As the amount of deformation will increase with the weight increase, an improvement in frontal crash is expected.

Table 1. FMVSS-305 Test Results

Vehicle Status FMVSS-305	Rating
Front Crash Simulation	Passed
Side Poll Crash Simulation	Conditional Passed

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